

Vestiges of Judeochristian Symbolism on a Mathematical Model to Construct Squaring the Circle

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Abstract

On this work its addressed a discussion about the meaning of god; its name on Jewish language, its relation with esoterism linked with gematria practice and a method given recently to define "squaring the circle" problem.

1 Historical Background

(Taken from wikipedia : Middle East; Ichtyis; Isopsephy and Gematria)

"Several major religions have their origins in the Middle East, including Judaism and Christianity. Throughout its history the Middle East has been a major center of world affairs; a strategically, economically, politically, culturally, and religiously sensitive area. The Near East (The Near East is a transcontinental region around the East Mediterranean encompassing parts of West Asia, the Balkans, and North Africa, including the historical Fertile Crescent, the Levant, Anatolia, East Thrace and Egypt.) was first largely unified under the Neo Assyrian Empire, then the Achaemenid Empire followed later by the Macedonian Empire and after this to some degree by the Iranian empires (namely the Parthian and Sassanid Empires), the Roman Empire and Byzantine Empire" .

"Among the earliest Christian symbols, that of the fish or Ichthys seems to have ranked first in importance, as seen on monumental sources such as tombs from the first decades of the 2nd century. After the fourth century the symbolism of the fish gradually disappeared; representations of fishes on baptismal fonts

and on bronze baptismal cups like those found at Rome and Trier, now in the Kircherian Museum, are merely of an ornamental character. The fish symbol was not, however, represented exclusively with symbols of the Eucharist; quite frequently it is found associated with such other symbols as the dove, the anchor, and the monogram of Christ. Also the monuments on which it appears, from the first to the fourth century, include frescoes, sculptured representations, rings, seals, gilded glasses, as well as enkolpia of various materials”.

By the other hand; Isopsephy involves reading words and sentences as numbers, assigning numerical instead of phonetic value to each letter of an alphabet. When read as numbers, they can be compared and contrasted with other words or phrases. It is supposed that according to Aristotle , isopsephy was part of the Pythagorean tradition based on the Milesian numbering of the Greek alphabet developed in the Greek city of Miletus, originated in the 6th century BCE. Similar systems have been used in other languages and cultures like is Hebrew gematria used in the Talmud and Midrash, and elaborately by many post-Talmudic commentators.

2 Mathematical Model

Diagram 1 shows a model to construct Ichtyus "fish" symbol taking as base 5 important points to draw "Squaring the Circle" scheme with only straightedge and compass. This model is very simple and in some way a kind of evident. If we try to remember another "mythological" square shapes; mention for example "Pegasus Galaxy" and some base of ancient pyramid we could suppose that "fish" could be considered a crossed cyclic quadrilaterals described on Euclidean geometry.

Diagram 1. Squaring the Circle and Ichthys Symbol; made with GeoEnzo 2024 and KPaint.

The Greek word Ichthys (fish) forming an acrostic for the Greek phrase Iesous Christos Theou Yios Soter;

Ἰησοῦς Χριστός, Θεοῦ Υἱός, Σωτήρ

i.e. Jesus Christ, Son of God, Savior, a concise summary of Christian faith.

By the other hand; even could appear that there is not enough bibliographical resources to establish a good framework to talk about " a practice of gematria" on ancient Jewish culture; next details, also showed on the scheme of

"Squaring the Circle" are very interesting due to the coincidence with some "spiritual" detail link to the concept of faith and the geometry of construction for the methodology use to "squaring the circle". I show two diagram to make evident the length of the angle on the line that cross the point D.

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Diagram 2. Squaring the Circle and "double edge word" = Yeshua + Mashiaj = 386 + 358 = 744 on centroid triangle found on angles of circle; made with GeoEnzo 2024 and KPaint.

when the number is introduced the searcher gives the word on Hebrew; same words can be translated on "google translate" to verify its meaning.

744 : = "I am Yeshua"

$$\frac{\text{י}}{10} \frac{\text{ש}}{300} \frac{\text{י}}{6} \frac{\text{ע}}{70} = 386 = \text{Jesus} = \text{ישוע}$$

$$\frac{\text{ח}}{40} \frac{\\text{ש}}{300} \frac{\text{י}}{10} \frac{\text{ח}}{8} = 358 = \text{messiah} = \text{משיח}$$

By the other hand, if we take the values use on the diagram we are going to write:

Two turns to the circle are equal to $(2)(360) = 720$ while to reach 744 we need to add 24° that is is equal to angle 384° .

$$* (2 \cdot 360) + 24 = 720 + 24 = 744$$

The value 384 is link with the word for "messiah"; when we use the value 358° and add 26° :

$$* 358 + 26 = 384 = 24$$

To add 26° degrees to 360° (angle value for one turn)

$$* 360 + 26 = 386$$

is equivalent by rotation of 2° degrees less to add

$$358 + 28 = 386$$

i.e. we obtain the word for Jesus (or Yeshua)

While angle 28° is linked with next addition

$$** 360 + (27 - 28) = 387 - 388$$

If we use the number equivalent to degree 24° ; i.e. 384° and add " π " we could establish

$$** 384 + \pi = 384 + 3.1416... = 387 - 388$$

3 Final Notes

On some references like [1] the text make mention to the concept of god and its relation with the number zero. There the author says that philosophically on ancient times; the importance of new mathematical notions about quantities were linked to the development and growth of certain religious groups since Greek to Middle East.

If well nowadays exist some difficulty into settle a good correlation of facts between the deification of some deity and an their tries to conceptualization since abstract objects like notions of measure; nature of something else; it is important to note that if like were suggested on other cites of the author of this manuscript; ancient cultures could knew some method to "squaring the circle" maybe one very similar to the presented here; then the connection between something non very well measurable like the quantity to define the number pi; could be use like inspiration to establish some meaning to the notion of god; in the sense given by phrases like "god is the alpha an omega" or "god can not be represented", maybe taken later by early Muslims to establish a characterization around prophet Muhammad (this is because he has no face).

About pi, if the meaning of "double edge" establish by the gematria for "I am Yesua" (i.e. "I am Good" or "I am Jesus") is linked with some quantities that until our days lacks of a full definition; then the sense of good like something infinite could be trace to such meaning.

Finally it is also important to note that both diagrams are integrated almost by the same points; and its on the "tail of the fish" where both schemes are interrelated.

4 References

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